

Supplementary Material

Host colonization dynamics under the host manipulation hypothesis

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1 Sensitivity analysis

To verify the robustness of our results, we ran a sensitivity analysis varying each parameter individually according to our reference values (see main text, Table 1). Each parameter was altered separately, while the remaining parameters were kept constant, allowing us to measure the individual influence of each parameter. For every variation, we calculated the metrics from the Results section (e.g., Figures 2 to 4), comparing them to our reference results. Figures S1 to S11 show the sensitivity analysis for host colonization frequency as a function of pathogen misfit, Figures S12 to S22 show host colonization frequency as a function of population-level accumulated capacity in absence of selective pressure, and Figures S23 to S31 show the sensitivity analysis for host colonization frequency as a function of population-level accumulated capacity under selective pressure.

Figure S1: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the average number of feeding events per insect, i.e., the simulation run with $b = 5$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $b = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S2: Frequency of a.) vector and b.) plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the carrying capacity per host, i.e., the simulation run with $K = 100$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $K = 20$ (dashed line).

Figure S3: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the multiplication rate of the phytoblast, i.e., the simulation run with $r = 6$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $r = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S4: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the phytoplasm mutation rate, i.e., the simulation run with $\delta = 0.2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\delta = 0.05$ (dashed line).

Figure S5: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in **a.)** and **b.)** respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts’ optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 1$ (dashed line).

Figure S6: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in **a.)** and **b.)** respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts’ optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S7: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S8: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S9: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 6$ (dashed line).

Figure S10: Frequency of a.) vector and b.) plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the initial condition, the simulation run with initially infected plants’ type selected randomly (“Reference” solid line in the graph and main text), and the second with simulations were run where the initially infected plants had the most extreme value of optimum phenotype (“Extreme” dashed line in the graph).

Figure S11: Frequency of **a.)** vector and **b.)** plant colonization as a function of pathogen misfit to the novel host for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. The misfit refers to the variation in the pathogen trait governing insect–pathogen interaction (phenotype V) and plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P) in a.) and b.) respectively. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all misfit values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of misfit (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that misfit (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the initial condition, the simulation run with initially infected plants’ type selected randomly (“Reference” solid line in the graph and main text), and the second with simulation was run where the initially infected plants had the optimum phenotype closest to the mean of the normal distribution that generated them (“Central” dashed line in the graph).

Figure S12: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the average number of feeding events per insect, i.e., the simulation run with $b = 5$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $b = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S13: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the carrying capacity per host, i.e., the simulation run with $K = 100$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $K = 20$ (dashed line).

Figure S14: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the multiplication rate of the phytoplasm, i.e., the simulation run with $r = 6$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $r = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S15: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the phytoplasma mutation rate, i.e., the simulation run with $\delta = 0.2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\delta = 0.05$ (dashed line).

Figure S16: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts’ optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 1$ (dashed line).

Figure S17: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts’ optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S18: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S19: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S20: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ (“Reference” solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 6$ (dashed line).

Figure S21: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the accumulated capacity in the absence of selective pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that accumulated capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the initial condition, the simulation run with initially infected plants’ type selected randomly (“Reference” solid line in the graph and main text), and the second with simulations were run where the initially infected plants had the most extreme value of optimum phenotype (“Extreme” dashed line in the graph).

Figure S22: Relationship between colonization frequency and accumulated capacity of the trait in the absence of host selective pressure for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation **a.)** frequency of plant colonization as a function of the capacity accumulated, in the absence of selection pressure in the pathogen population while multiplying in a vector that interacts with the colonized plant, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing plant–pathogen interaction (phenotype P). **b.)** frequency of vector colonization as a function of the capacity accumulated, in the absence of selection pressure, in the pathogen population while multiplying in a plant that interacts with the colonized vector, where capacity refers to variation in the pathogen trait governing vector–pathogen interaction (phenotype V). Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the initial condition, the simulation run with initially infected plants’ type selected randomly (“Reference” solid line in the graph and main text), and the second with simulation was run where the initially infected plants had the optimum phenotype closest to the mean of the normal distribution that generated them (“Central” dashed line in the graph).

Figure S23: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values equals one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the average number of feeding events per insect, i.e., the simulation run with $b = 5$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $b = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S24: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the carrying capacity per host, i.e., the simulation run with $K = 100$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $K = 20$ (dashed line).

Figure S25: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the multiplication rate of the phytoplasma, i.e., the simulation run with $r = 6$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $r = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S26: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the phytoplasma mutation rate, i.e., the simulation run with $\delta = 0.2$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $\delta = 0.05$ (dashed line).

Figure S27: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts' optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 1$ (dashed line).

Figure S28: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the standard deviation of the normal distributions that generate the hosts' optimum phenotypes, the simulation run with $\sigma = 2$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $\sigma = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S29: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 2$ (dashed line).

Figure S30: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 4$ (dashed line).

Figure S31: Accumulated capacity under selection in the pathogen population while infecting a plant and prior to a novel vector-plant interaction for both scenarios, with (orange curve) and without (blue curve) host manipulation. Both curves are normalized, which means the sum of the probability of host colonization occurring for all accumulated capacity values is equal to one. Thus, for a given value of accumulated capacity (x-axis), we have the probability of a host colonization occurring with that capacity accumulation prior to the colonization event (y-axis). The figure compares the results from two simulation runs that differ in the host manipulation effect on the probability of interaction between insect and plant with opposite infection status, the simulation run with $W = 10$ ("Reference" solid line and main text) and the second with $W = 6$ (dashed line).